

Mercuration of Higher Aromatic Hydrocarbons.

Part I.

BY M. GOSWAMI AND H. N. DAS-GUPTA.

Various organo-mercuric compounds having mercury attached directly to the carbon atom of aliphatic or aromatic radicles have been prepared. In recent years attention has been directed more to the preparation of mercuri-aromatic compounds containing as low a percentage of mercury as possible, as, for therapeutic purposes, barring toxicity, they have been found in their bactericidal activity far superior to organo-arsenic compounds—the toxicity being due to the high percentage of mercury which must be diminished to the lowest possible limit before it could be used successfully in therapeutics. With this end in view the compounds described in this paper were prepared by the method of Dimroth (*Ber.*, 1898, 31, 2154; 1899, 32, 758). It appears from literature, that except in the cases of benzene, naphthalene and diphenyl, no attempt has been made to prepare mercury derivatives of higher aromatic hydrocarbons.

Anthracene, phenanthrene, acenaphthene and fluorene all gave the corresponding monomercurichloride compounds and of these the last two gave the corresponding mercurihydroxides whilst the mercurichlorides of anthracene and phenanthrene failed to produce similar hydroxides by the ordinary method. These mercurihydroxides behave generally like the ordinary aromatic mercurihydroxides evolving ammonia from ammonium chloride. The position which is taken up by the mercury atom has not yet been settled and we propose to undertake this problem in the near future. Determinations of toxicity and therapeutic index of the compounds are in progress.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Acenaphthene Mercurichloride.—Acenaphthene (10 g.) and mercuric acetate (24 g.) were dissolved in acetic acid (70 c.c.) and

the solution was heated under pressure in an oil-bath to 115-20° for 5 hours. During this period the colour of the solution turned red. This was then allowed to cool whereby some unacted acenaphthene together with mercurous acetate separated out. The filtrate from the unchanged mass, etc., was now evaporated to one third the original volume and was treated with alcoholic calcium chloride solution after cooling. This resulted in the precipitation of a slightly pink-coloured compound which was filtered and the residue was repeatedly washed with water and alcohol and finally with ether. The mass was then dried in a vacuum desiccator; the dried mass thus obtained was pinkish-white in colour. It melts with decomposition at 148° (yield 80 per cent.). It is insoluble in most of the common organic solvents. (Found: Hg, 50.59, 51.05; Cl, 9.06. $C_{12}H_9HgCl$ requires Hg, 51.32; Cl, 9.12 per cent.).

Anthracene Mercurichloride.—Mercuric acetate (10 g.) and anthracene (5 g.) were first of all dissolved in acetic acid (45 c.c.) and the solution was heated under pressure to 130-40° and kept at that temperature for 7-8 hours. In course of one hour the whole of anthracene went into solution which assumed a deep red colour. On allowing to cool the resulting product solidified *en masse*. The solidified mass was treated with more acetic acid and heated on water-bath whereby most of the solids went into solution. The solution was filtered while hot and the filtrate was concentrated to two-third the original volume and at once treated with alcoholic calcium chloride whereby an immediate precipitation occurred. This precipitate was washed successively with water, alcohol, and ether and then dried in a vacuum desiccator. Anthracene mercurichloride is greyish-yellow in colour and melts with decomposition at 181-83°. It is sparingly soluble in benzene and is insoluble in most of the organic solvents; yield 30 per cent. (Found: Hg, 47.57, 48.02; Cl, 8.4. $C_{14}H_9HgCl$ requires Hg, 48.71; Cl, 8.59 per cent.).

Phenanthrene Mercurichloride.—A mixture consisting of phenanthrene (5 g.), mercuric acetate (10 g.) and acetic acid (40 c.c.) was heated in an oil-bath in a pressure flask to a temperature of 120-25° for 4 hours. The resulting yellowish-brown solution was separated from mercurous chloride by filtration. The filtrate was concentrated and allowed to cool and then treated with alcoholic calcium chloride solution. The resulting white precipitate

was separated by filtration and then washed successively with water, alcohol and finally with ether and then dried in vacuum. The compound is a white amorphous powder melting with decomposition at 155-57°. Like the previous mercury compounds it is also insoluble in common organic solvents, yield 40%. (Found: Hg, 47.97, 48.1; Cl, 8.51. $C_{14}H_9HgCl$ requires Hg, 48.71; Cl, 8.59 per cent.).

Fluorene Mercurichloride.—A mixture consisting of fluorene (5 g.), mercuric acetate (12 g.) and acetic acid (35 c.c.) was heated to a temperature of 120-30° for 6-7 hours in a pressure flask. The dissolution of fluorene was gradual and was complete in course of 4-6 hours after which the mixture was heated for two hours more. On allowing to cool a small quantity of unchanged fluorene separated. This was filtered off and the filtrate evaporated to half the original volume and cooled. A white precipitate resulted on the addition of alcoholic calcium chloride solution. The precipitated fluorene mercurichloride was separated, washed repeatedly with water alcohol and ether and then dried in vacuum. The compound melts with decomposition at 130-132° (yield 80%). It is very slightly soluble in acetone and hot acetic acid, is insoluble in all other common organic solvents. (Found: Hg, 49.76; Cl, 8.81. $C_{13}H_9HgCl$ requires Hg, 49.93; Cl, 8.84 per cent.).

Fluorene Mercurihydroxide.—About 50 c.c. of alcohol were taken in a conical flask provided with an upright condenser, and finely powdered fluorene mercurichloride (4 g.) was suspended in it to which moist silver oxide prepared from 2.5 g. of silver nitrate was added. The whole was then heated on a water-bath for 8 hours and then allowed to stand overnight. The alcoholic solution was separated from the silver chloride and silver oxide and other substances by filtration. The filtrate was first concentrated whereby it became turbid due to the separation of some mechanically carried silver salt. This was separated and the filtrate was then evaporated to dryness on a water-bath. The residue thus obtained was of slightly dark colour and was therefore recrystallised from alcohol when a yellowish-white microcrystalline product was obtained. The compound decomposes at 145-47°. It is soluble in water and alcohol but is insoluble in other organic solvents. The aqueous solution is very faintly alkaline to litmus. Its basic character is further proved by its liberation of ammonia from ammonium salts, (yield 10%). (Found: Hg, 51.98. $C_{13}H_9HgOH$ requires Hg, 52.3 per cent.).

Acenaphthene Mercurihydroxide.—Silver nitrate (3 g.) was converted into silver oxide and then washed free of alkali. The moist silver oxide together with 50 c.c. of alcohol and finely powdered acenaphthene mercurichloride (3 g.) was heated under reflux for 14-15 hours on the water-bath. The mass was filtered and the filtrate was concentrated and allowed to cool when a colourless microcrystalline product separated out. The product was dried in a vacuum desiccator. The yield, in this case also, is very small.

The hydroxide is a strong base ; its alcoholic solution turns red litmus blue and it liberates ammonia from ammonium salts and absorbs carbon dioxide from air. It is soluble in alcohol and hot benzene, sparingly in ether, acetone and hot toluene. When heated it shrinks at 175° and melts at 184°. (Found : Hg, 53·95. $C_{14}H_9Hg$ OH requires Hg, 54·05 per cent.).

Neither anthracene nor phenanthrene mercurichloride gave any hydroxide derivatives. Analogous treatment resulted in the total disruption of the molecule.

DEPARTMENT OF APPLIED CHEMISTRY,
UNIVERSITY COLLEGE OF SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY,
CALCUTTA.

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